

Stretching of DNA Molecules on Mica Surfaces by Magnetic Field

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Abstract - This paper presents a method for the stretching of DNA molecules on mica surfaces by magnetic field. In the experiment, the magnetic fields with different intensities were generated using a self-made cylindrical coil and were used to study their effects on DNA molecules. The magnetic field intensity was controlled by the electric current flowing through the coil. The imaging of DNA molecules was performed by atomic force microscope (AFM) in the same position on the mica surface after the treatment with the magnetic field. It was found that the DNA molecules were gradually straightened with the increase of magnetic field intensity, and the straightening performance was better than that of the molecular combing method. In addition, the degree of DNA straightening was related to the speed at which DNA molecules were dropped to the mica surface, the amount of DNA charges and the direction of magnetic field.

Keywords—*Magnetic field; DNA; Atomic force microscope (AFM)*

I. INTRODUCTION

The study of DNA molecules on the nanometer scale is one of the hotspots in the fields of biology and clinical medicine as it is a unique carrier of genetic information. The DNA molecule is also a natural nano material which has great potential in the field of molecular devices. DNA molecules are becoming more and more important in nano science and technology [1]. However, based on the fact that DNA molecules are irregularly curled in solutions, stretching DNA molecules on a surface by means of effective techniques is one of the critical steps in single DNA molecule analysis [2-3]. Research work shows that the stretching of DNA molecules on the substrate surface is the basis for in-depth study [4-5]. In recent years, many methods such as magnetic tweezers [6-8], optical tweezers [9-11], blowing method [12], centrifugal method [13], and molecular combing [14-16] have been developed for the stretching of DNA molecules. In addition, the method of stretching DNA is generally combined with other methods including microfluidic [17-18], electrophoresis [19], and fluorescence imaging [20-22]. Typically, stretching a DNA molecule is that one end of the DNA molecule is attached to the substrate surface and is extended by various weak forces such as optical force, electric force and surface tension [23]. In this work, a simple approach to the stretching of DNA molecules is introduced, and the method is based on the magnetic treatment of DNA molecules and AFM imaging.

II. EXPERIMENT

A. Materials

DNA solutions ($500 \text{ ng}\cdot\mu\text{L}^{-1}$, 48,502 base pairs) were purchased from Changchun Nachuan Technology Company (China). Mica sheets were purchased from TaiYuan Fluorophlogopite Mica Company, and they were used for the substrates of DNA samples. Teslameter was purchased from Shanghai Hengtong magnetolectric Technology Company, and they were used to measure the magnetic field intensity. Images of DNA molecules were acquired by AFM system working in the contact mode.

B. Methods

In the experiments, a cylindrical coil was designed and constructed to generate the magnetic field. The teslameter was used to measure the magnetic field intensity in the center of coil with different currents and record the data. A freshly cleaved mica sheet was placed on the coil center to ensure that the sample was in a constant magnetic field. The mica sheet was always in the same position during all experiments. The DNA solution was diluted to $10 \text{ ng}\cdot\mu\text{L}^{-1}$ with the TE buffer and dropped onto the mica surface for 15 min. The air-dried sample was then removed and it was placed into a petri dish. After the samples were made following the above steps, the imaging of DNA molecules was performed by AFM on the mica surface.

C. Magnetic field intensity

The magnetic field distribution of the coil is shown in Fig. 1(a). The electric current flowing through the coil will generate the magnetic field inside and outside the coil. Fig. 1(b) shows the equivalent diagram for the calculation of the magnetic field.

Fig. 1 (a) Cylindrical coil and its magnetic field distribution. (b) Equivalent diagram (L is the coil length, I is the current, and r is the radius).

Assuming that L is the total coil length and I is the electric current and taking the coil axis as the Z -axis, where the midpoint is the origin, Q is the point on the Z -axis, the direction of magnetic field is parallel to the Z -axis. The magnetic field intensity can be calculated by the Biot-Savart law [24]

$$dB = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{I d\vec{l} \times \vec{R}}{R^2} \quad (1)$$

and

$$B = \oint_L dB = \oint_L \frac{\mu_0 I}{4\pi} \frac{d\vec{l} \times \vec{R}}{R^2} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ T}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{A}^{-1}$ (the absolute magnetic permeability of vacuum or air), B (in mT) is the magnetic field intensity, I (in A) is the electric current flowing through the coil, $d\vec{l}$ is a current element. Since $d\vec{l} \perp \vec{R}$ and $R^2 = r^2 + z^2$, Eq. (2) becomes

$$B = \frac{\mu_0}{2} \frac{I r^2}{(r^2 + z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \vec{k} \quad (3)$$

where \vec{k} is the unit vector vertical to the circular path surface. The direction of symmetric axis is consistent with the direction of the magnetic field. According to the right-hand rule, the Z -axis direction is the direction of the magnetic field intensity B .

The magnetic field intensity B is

$$B = \frac{\mu_0}{2} \frac{I r^2}{(r^2 + z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (4)$$

In the experiments, the sample was placed on the mica surface at the coil center. For $z=0$, Eq. (3) can be rewritten as

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2r} \quad (5)$$

The magnetic field intensity at the center is the sum of the magnetic field intensity from an N -turn coil. The magnetic field intensity can be expressed as

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 I N}{2r} \quad (6)$$

where N is the number of coil turns, and r is the radius of coil (in m).

The magnetic field intensity could produce some deviation due to the unideal coil. Assuming that the deviation is P , the total magnetic field intensity is B' , then $B' = B + P$. The deviation can be obtained by Teslameter and MATLAB software. Before the experiment, the relationship between the current and magnetic field intensity was measured by Teslameter, as shown in Table 1. The curve fitting is $y = 4.8851x + 0.0301$.

Table 1 Relationship between the current and the magnetic field intensity

Current (A)	0.015	0.035	0.055	0.075	0.095	0.117	0.138
Magnetic field intensity (mT)	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7

By substituting the value of μ_0 , N and r in Eq. (6), the theoretical value of the magnetic field intensity is

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 I N}{2r} = 4.8891I \quad (7)$$

The deviation between the theoretically calculated and the measured magnetic field intensity values was within the error range (the root-mean-square error is 0.0040), so magnetic field intensity is

$$B' = 4.8851I + 0.0301 \quad (8)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, the images of DNA molecules were performed by AFM in the same position on the mica surfaces to study the effect of magnetic field on DNA molecules, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 AFM images of DNA molecules stretched on mica surfaces under different conditions. Scan size: $15.0 \mu\text{m} \times 15.0 \mu\text{m}$. (a) Without a magnetic field. (b-i) With the magnetic fields generated by the currents of 0.01A, 0.05A, 0.10A, 0.15A, 0.20A, 0.25A, 0.30A, and 0.35A. (j) Molecular combing technique.

Fig. 2(a) shows the morphology of DNA molecules without a magnetic field. Figs. 2(b-i) show the DNA strands were stretched as a line pattern in the magnetic field. According to Eq. (7), the magnetic field intensities of the samples under different currents were shown in Table 2. In addition, according to the fitting of straight lines, the root-mean-square error (RMSE) of the DNA strands was shown in Table 2. The RMSE was used to measure the deviation between the observed value and the true value, which can largely reflect the precision of the measurement. A small RMSE value indicated a good straightening performance. Table 2 shows that the RMSE is gradually reduced, and the DNA molecules were gradually straightened with the increase of magnetic field intensity. Fig. 2(j) shows that the images of DNA molecules stretched by molecular combing method, and the RMSE is 2.281. Figs. 2(i)-2(j) and RMSE show that the straightening performance of DNA molecules with the magnetic field was better than that of the molecular combing method. In addition, the stretching of DNA molecules on mica surfaces by magnetic field does not require ion-modified substrates, making samples simple and reproducible.

Table 2 Magnetic field intensity and RMSE value under different currents

Current (A)	0.01	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.35
Magnetic induction intensity (mT)	0.079	0.274	0.519	0.763	1.007	1.251	1.496	1.740
RMSE	65.499	35.994	13.132	11.270	9.462	9.174	2.704	0.987

When the DNA solution dropped to the mica surface, a phosphoric acid group on the DNA chain can be equivalent to a negative charge. In the case of a uniform magnetic field, the negative charge enters the magnetic field at an initial velocity and is affected by the Lorentz force. The force is

$$f = qvB \sin \theta \quad (9)$$

where θ is the angle between v and B . q is the particle charge and v is the initial velocity. When the negative charge entered the magnetic field at the initial velocity v . The velocity direction was perpendicular to the magnetic field

intensity B , and the trajectories of the particles can only be in this plane. The Lorentz force only changes the motion direction of the particles. The particles are circularly moved at a constant speed by the Lorentz force in the magnetic field, as shown in Fig. 3(a).

Fig. 3 Movement of particles in the magnetic field. (a) Particles are circularly moved. (b) Helix movement.

When the charged particles enter the magnetic field at an arbitrary angle θ between the magnetic field intensity B and the initial velocity v , the initial velocity v can be decomposed into the component of vertical to B ($v_{\perp} = v \sin \theta$) and the component of parallel to B ($v_{\parallel} = v \cos \theta$). Because there is a vertical component v_{\perp} , the particles can move on a plane of perpendicular to B . The Lorentz force parallel to B is zero, so the presence of the parallel component v_{\parallel} only causes the particles at the direction parallel to B linearly moved. When there are the velocity component v_{\perp} and the parallel component v_{\parallel} , the particles not only move around the magnetic field intensity B for the cyclotron movement, but also move linearly along the magnetic field intensity direction (or the opposite direction), so the movement of particles is helix movement (the synthetic motion of the two movements), as shown in Fig. 3(b).

The phosphate group on the DNA strands undergoes a deflection movement in the magnetic field by Lorentz force. When the viscous ends of the DNA molecule is absorbed to the mica surface, the phosphoric acid group of the DNA strand will deflect at the viscous end as a fixed point and the DNA molecules can be straightened due to the repulsive force

of the equal charge. In the same magnetic field strength, the deflection direction of the DNA was affected by several factors, such as initial velocity at which DNA molecules were dropped onto the mica surface, the direction of the magnetic field and the amount of DNA charges, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 DNA molecules in the same magnetic field.

IV. CONCLUSION

By analyzing the images of DNA molecules obtained in the experiments, conclusions can be made that the DNA molecules were gradually straightened with the increase of magnetic field intensity. While, the degree of DNA straightening was related to the speed at which DNA molecules were dropped onto the mica surface, the direction of magnetic field and the amount of DNA charges. Compared to the molecular combing method used to straighten DNA molecules commonly, the manipulation method proposed in this work is simple and the DNA molecules can be straightened obviously. In addition, this method has its potential for applications such as DNA sequencing, gene editing and molecular devices.

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